

**DIAGNOSING EXISTING AND PREFERRED ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE OF
S.S.C, C.B.S.E AND I.C.S.E BOARDS OF MUMBAI****Reema Sharma**

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Abstract

The foundation of any organization is its culture. Organisational Culture is a unique constellation of values, belief, vision and mission which is created, inculcated, shared and enriched by the people working there. Every corporate organisation has its own culture with varied dynamics. Can schools be far behind when they are microcosms of activity? With administrative units, teaching and non teaching staff, students, parents and attached services schools cater to a number of small organisational structures within the main organisation. It is not a surprise that schools have developed organisational cultures in them. There are mainly three types of educational board in Mumbai city viz S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E. The present study focuses on to study which type of Organisational culture exists and preferred in an educational organization with respect to the dimensions - Power culture, Role culture, Achievement culture and Support culture. Every organization has some combination of these four basic organizational cultures. For this study data was collected through a reliable and valid tool which was administered on a sample of 570 secondary school teachers of Mumbai. This research paper is a report of the secondary school teachers' perception of the existing and preferred culture in S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E boards.

Keywords: *Organisational Culture; Power Culture; Role Culture; Achievement Culture and Support Culture*

Introduction

Organisational Culture

“Culture is to an organization what personality is to an individual”

(Harrison & Stokes)¹

Can success of an organization be attributed to its culture? Culture is one aspect that is not tangible, yet it plays a very important role in the success of an organisation. The crux of the culture is formed by the values, belief, vision and mission which are not visible but are consciously and deliberately cultivated shared and enriched by the employee (teachers) working there. Culture is the mode by which an organization expresses itself to its employees (teachers). Organisational culture has gained great importance in the 21st century, because of its impact on teacher's performance, job satisfaction and commitment. It is vital for every organisation to figure out its own dynamic culture so that managers (principal) can capitalize on the insights generated by the cultural outlook to exercise greater control over their organisations. Organisational culture can be seen as the “social glue that helps hold the organization together by providing appropriate standards for what employees should say and do” (Robbins, 1996:687). An organisation culture also differentiates it from other organisation and may explain why employees are attracted to it and are less likely to leave (O'Reilly, Chatman and Caldwell, 1991; Smith, 2003). According to Sathe (1983:12) organisational culture provides “guiding principles” that can have an impact on employee behaviour in terms of communication, cooperation, commitment, decision making and implementation. O'Reilly *et al.* (1991) have found that organisational culture can play a role in how well an employee fits into an organization relating to their level of commitment and satisfaction. It has been asserted that the strength of organisational culture can impact on the performance of firms (Deal and Kennedy, 1982; Denison, 1984; Kotter and Heskett, 1992). In the present study the researcher is studying what type of culture exist and preferred in S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E board with respect to the dimensions of organizational culture- Power culture, Role culture, Achievement culture and

¹ Harrison,R & Stokes,H., Diagnosing Organisational Culture, San Francisco: Published by Pfeiffer.,1992.

Support culture. Researcher is also studying whether there is any difference in the existing and preferred culture of schools of S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E boards of Mumbai.

Operational definitions:

Organisational Culture: - Organisational culture is the set of values, belief, principles and goals which the teacher abides, for the smooth running of the organisation. Organisation cultures focus is based on four dimensions, namely power, role, achievement and support.

- ✓ **Power dimension:** Describes an organisational culture that is based on inequality of access to resources. It has a single source of power from which rays of influence spread throughout the organisation. This means that power is centralised and organisational members are connected to the centre by functional and specialist strings.
- ✓ **Role dimension:** This type of culture focuses mainly on job description and specialisation. In other words, work is controlled by procedures and rules that underlie the job description, which is more important than the person who fills the position.
- ✓ **Achievement dimension:** This often refers to a task culture, which entails organisational members focusing on realising the set purpose and goals of the organisation. The main strategic objective of this culture is to bring the right people together, in order to achieve the organisational goals.
- ✓ **Support dimension:** Describes an organisational climate that is based on mutual trust between the individual and the organisation. A support-oriented organisation exists solely for the individuals who comprise it, and may be represented diagrammatically as a cluster in which no individual dominates.

Aim of the study

To Study the Existing and Preferred Organisational Culture of S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E boards.

Objective of the Study

1. To study what type of culture is exist in S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E board with respect to the dimensions of organisational culture.

2. To study what type of culture is preferred in S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E board with respect to the dimensions of organisational culture.

Methodology

Design of the study

Descriptive method of survey type was used.

Sample

The sample comprised of 570 secondary school teachers from Mumbai of S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E boards.

Research instrument

- ✓ **Organisational culture scale (OCS) prepared by Harrison and Stokes (1992)**

According to Harrison (1993: 27) the reliabilities of the four dimensions of the organisational culture questionnaire, calculated by the Spearman-Brown formula, are for achievement (0.86), power (0.90), role (0.64) and support (0.87). The overall reliability of the questionnaire is 0.85 (Harrison 1993).

Results

(I)

Table: 1.1

EXISTING ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE			
E.O.C	S.S.C	C.B.S.E	I.C.S.E
POWER CULTURE	48.9	28.2	27.1
ROLE CULTURE	37.3	49.4	37.5
ACHIEVEMENT CULTURE	28.8	34.3	49.5
SUPPORT CULTURE	34.9	37.9	35.8

Figure: 1.1

Conclusion: (a) In **S.S.C** board the mean scores of Power culture is 48.9, Role culture is 37.3, Achievement culture is 28.8 and Support culture is 34.9. Therefore, we can conclude that **Power** culture is prevailing in S.S.C board.

(b) In **C.B.S.E** board the mean scores of Power culture is 28.2, Role culture is 49.4, Achievement culture is 34.3 and Support culture is 37.9. Therefore, we can conclude that **Role** culture is prevailing in C.B.S.E board.

(c) In **I.C.S.E** board the mean scores of Power culture is 27.1, Role culture is 37.5, Achievement culture is 49.5 and Support culture is 35.8. Therefore, we can conclude that **Achievement** culture is prevailing in I.C.S.E board.

Discussion: (a) In S.S.C board power culture exist which reflects an inequality of access to resources. This definitely means that this system is very strong on the hierarchies and position of employees in their organization. Leadership resides in one person and it rests on the ability of the person to take the organisation forward. Employees in power culture are motivated by rewards and punishments.

(b) In C.B.S E board role culture exist which is based on a system of structures and procedures. The struggle for power is moderated by laws. Each level in the organization has a definite area of authority, and work can continue to be done without direct supervision from the top. This culture also depends a lot on rewards and punishments.

(c) In I.C.S.E board Achievement culture exist which depends a lot on the personal energy of the employees. It runs more on the commitment and happiness of the employee rather than rewards and punishments. This happiness stems from the fact that the employees are intrinsically motivated to work. Such culture lines people up to a common goal, vision and purpose.

(II)

Table 1.2

PREFERED ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE			
P.O.C	S.S.C	C.B.S.E	I.C.S.E
POWER CULTURE	27.5	25	32.3
ROLE CULTURE	33.8	36.2	30.2
ACHIEVEMENT CULTURE	40.3	41.8	41.9
SUPPORT CULTURE	48.2	46.9	45.5

Figure 1.2

Conclusion: (a) In S.S.C board the mean scores of Power culture is 27.5, Role culture is 33.8, Achievement culture is 40.3 and Support culture is 48.2. Therefore, we can conclude that in S.S.C board teachers prefer Support and Achievement culture.

(b) In C.B.S.E board the mean scores of Power culture is 25, Role culture is 36.2, Achievement culture is 41.8 and Support culture is 46.9. Therefore, we can conclude that in C.B.S.E board teachers prefer Support and Achievement culture.

(c) In I.C.S.E board the mean scores of Power culture is 32.3, Role culture is 30.2, Achievement culture is 41.9 and Support culture is 45.5. Therefore, we can conclude that in I.C.S.E board teachers prefer Support and Achievement culture.

Discussion: In all the 3 boards S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E, teachers preferred support culture followed by Achievement culture. Support culture is based on mutual trust between the individual and the organisation. Employees believe they are valued as human beings and not as just cogs in a bigger machine. They feel cared for and hence are more human in their interactions with other people: parents, colleagues, students, management etc. There is an intrinsic motivation to work for the vision of the organization. Employees contribute out of sense of commitment to organisation for which they feel a real sense of belonging and in which they believe they have a personal stake.

Conclusion:

The organizational culture is the mirror of the organization. There was a difference found in the existing and preferred culture of S.S.C, C.B.S.E and I.C.S.E boards of Mumbai. Knowledge about once organizational culture will help the manager (principal) to avoid dominance by any one of the four cultures and choose a dynamic balance in which each culture is expressed in its highest form and the positive side of each balance the darker tendencies of the others. Culture is achieved by debate within the organization between different perceptions of what is good for the organization and for its stakeholders. It shows to the stake holders like the

parents, employee and the community what the school believes in and how their personal values match with those of the school.

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